

A Critical Appraisal on *Shleepada* in *Ayurveda*

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ABSTRACT

Shleepada is *Kapha Pradhana Tridoshaja Vyadhi* which manifests by vitiating *Mamsa, Kapha* and *Rakta* and it leads to abnormal enlargement of different body parts. *Dusta Jala* is considered to be one of the prime causes of *Shleepada* which manifests with the symptoms of fever, painful swelling starting from groin and extending to the feet. It is classified into three types as *Vataja, Pittaja* and *Kaphaja*. Some *Acharyas* opine that *Shleepada* manifests to the other body parts like hands, ears, eyes, penis, lips and nose. *Ayurveda* though provides therapeutic measures for disease, it emphasis more on maintenance and promotion of health. The present article reviews the concept of *Shleepada* enunciated in *Samhitas*.

KEYWORDS: *Dusta Jala, Kapha Dosha, Shleepada, Types of Shleepada*

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INTRODUCTION

Shleepada is categorised under *Krimi Vijnanam*.^[1] '*Shleepadam Iti Shilaavat Padam*' a pathological condition which means foot will be turned hard like a stone.^[2] This condition mostly affects the *Twak* (skin). *Rohini* is the sixth layer of *Twak* with thickness equivalent to *Vrihi Pramana* (thickness of Rice) and is regarded as the seat of *Granthi, Apache, Arbudha, Shleepada* and *Galaganda*.^[3] Detailed review on *Shleepada* has been mentioned in *Bruhatrayee* and *Laghutrayee*. Water from *Paariyaatra, Vindya, Sahya* ranges causes *Shiroroga, Hridroga, Kushta* and *Shleepada*.^[4] Water from *Mahendra Mountain* produces *Shleepada* and *Udararoga* whereas water of *Himavat Mountain* causes *Hridroga, Kshvathu, Shiroroga, Shleepada* and *Galaganda*.^[5] *Shleepada* develops in cold climate and due to *Dusta Jala* (contaminated Water) which causes vitiation of *Vata, Pitta, Kapha* leading to *Adhogamana* of *Prakupita Doshas* which get localized in groin, thigh, foreleg, calves and gradually reaches to the foot giving rise to *Shopha* associated with *Arati* (Pain), *Jwara* (Pyrexia) and turns hard in consistency.^[6,7] *Acharya Sushruta* has mentioned that *Shotha* can occur in *Karna, Netra, Shishna, Oshtha* and *Nasa*. *Shleepada* has been classified into three types as *Vataja, Pittaja* and *Kaphaja*. This disease does not manifest without the involvement of *Kapha Dosha*.^[6] If *Shleepada* persists for more than one year and it grows bigger in size resembling to that of an ant hill and exudates fluid associated with *Kandu* (itching) and *Srava* (discharge) it is termed as *Asadhya* (incurable).^[6,8]

Aims and Objectives

To review and analyse the concept of *Shleepada* in *Ayurvedic* texts

Material and Methods

In present study different concepts on *Shleepada* has been reviewed, compiled from existing *Ayurvedic* literature, various research journals and authentic internet sources. Further the concepts are analysed and understanding has been put forth in regards to proposed title.

DISCUSSION

Nidana (Etiological Factors)

Detailed review on *Nidana* (Etiological factors) has been mentioned in *Bruhatrayee* and *Laghutrayee*. *Shleepada* has been mentioned under *Krimi Vijnana*.^[1] Stagnated Water of *Paariyaatra, Vindya, Sahya* (Southern Branch of Western Ghats), stagnated water of *Mahendra Mountains* (Northern Branch of Western Ghats), *Himalaya, Dushita Desha, Kala, Jala, Mithya Ahara* (incompatible dietary intake) are responsible for manifestation of *Shleepada*.^[4-6]

Bhava Prakasha has commented that water from *Sahya Range* (Example Godavari and Krishna River) may cause *Twak Vikaras* and vitiates *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha*.^[9] *Acharya Vagbhata* opines that stagnated water from *Himalayas, Vindya, Sahya, Mahendra Mountains* mitigates *Doshas*, bestows the strength, sexual vigour and vitiates *Tridosha*.^[10] *Acharya Bhela* has mentioned it under

Janapadodwamsa Vyadhi where habitual intake of *Matsyanna* in *Prachya Pradesha* (Bengal, Assam, Manipur, Nagaland, Mizoram, Arunachal Pradesh) causes prevalence of *Kapha Pitta* ailments like *Galaganda* and *Shleepada*.^[11] He mentioned *Dadhi* (Curd) as a cause of *Shleepada*.^[12] *Matsya* (fish) possesses *Snigdha*, *Guru Guna*, *Madhura Rasa*, *Bahudoshakara* and *Vatahara properties*.^[13]

In *Anupa Desha*, due to heavy rainfall there will be stagnation of water in large quantity which has been put forth as *Nidana* for *Shleepada*.^[6,14] *Anupa Desha* always surrounds with thick forest where the cold wind blows. The land is predominant with *Kapha Dosha* and *Kapha* Predominant *Vyadhi*^[15] and water of *Anupa Desha* is *Anekadosham*, *Abhishyandi* and *Ahitam*.^[16] It possesses *Madhura Rasa*, *Snigdha*, *Guru* and *Abhishyandi Guna*. It is *Agninashaka* and *Kaphakara* in

nature.^[17] *Madhura Rasa* bestows *Preenana*, *Jeevana*, *Tarpana*, *Sthairya* and *Bruhmana Karma* and if consumed excessively produces *Kapha Vikaras*. *Snigdha Guna* is *Sleshma Vardaka*, *Guru Guna* diminishes the *Agni* and eliminates *Vata Dosha* with increase in *Kapha*. *Abhishyandi Guna* brings about excessive *Kleda* in body and causes obstruction to *Srotas*.^[18] Water is the sustainer of life and stagnant water can be comprehended with *Dusta Jala*.^[19] *Sushruta* opines that polluted water should not be consumed as they will aggravate the *Doshas* and leads to manifestation of deadly diseases.^[20] *Mithya Ahara Vihara* and *Dusta Jala*^[6] exhibit the *Kapha Pitta Kara*^[19] property. Hence *Nidanas* play a key role in causing *Shleepada*.^[21] The assessment of *Nidana* varies as per person; here generally the evaluation of *Nidana* has been done in regards to *Shleepada* (Table 1).

A. Sannikrusta Nidana	<i>Kaphaja Ahara Vihara, Dusta Jala Sevana</i>
B. Viprakrusta Nidana	<i>Sheeta Kala, Anupa Desha</i>
A. Vyabhichari Hetu	<i>Sheeta Kala, Anupa Desha</i>
B. Pradhanika Hetu	<i>Kaphakara Ahara, Dusta Jala sevana</i>
A. Utpadaka Hetu	In cold climate, due to <i>Kaphakara Ahara Vihara, Kapha Dosha Prakopa</i>
B. Vyanjaka Hetu	Accumulated <i>Kapha</i> manifests disorders of <i>Kapha</i>
A. Dosha Hetu	<i>Vata - Jala</i> from <i>Sahya</i> range <i>Pitta</i> - Water from <i>Anupa Desha</i> <i>Kapha- Kaphavardhaka Ahara Vihara, Justa Jala Sevana</i>
B. Vyadhi Hetu	<i>Kaphakara Ahara Vihara, Dushita Jala Sevana</i>
C. Ubhaya Hetu	Water from <i>Anupa Desha, Kaphavardhaka Ahara, Justa Jala Sevana</i>
A. Bahya Hetu	<i>Kaphadosha Prakopaka Hetu (Dadhi, Matsya, Dusta Jala)</i>
B. Abhyantara Hetu	<i>Tridoshaja</i>
A. Asatmendriyartham Samyoga	-
B. Prajnapradha	<i>Adharma (Janapadodwamsa)</i>
C. Parinama	<i>Sheeta Kala</i>
A. Anubandha Hetu	<i>Vata, Pitta Dosha</i>
B. Anubandhya Hetu	<i>Kapha Dosha (Dusta Jala Sevana, Kaphakara Ahara Vihara)</i>

Purvarupa (Prodromal Symptoms)

Purvarupa of *Shleepada* has not been explained in *Ayurveda* classics.

Lakshanas (Symptoms)

On *Nidana Sevana*, when *Dosha Dushya Sammurchana* occurs, the *Lakshanas* (symptoms) will get manifested. In *Sleepada* '*Shila Vat Shopham*' (hardening like a stone) can be taken as cardinal feature along with symptoms like *Jwara*, pain in groin region^[6-7] (Table 2A).

Shopham^[18,19]: Consumption of *Mithya Ahara Vihara* leads to *Tridosha Dushti*. *Kapha Dosha* is predominant of *Jala Mahabhuta* and *Prithvi Mahabhuta*. Due to *Sneha Samana Guna* of *Kapha*, *Pitta* also gets vitiated. With an increase in *Drava Guna* of *Pitta* occurs *Agni Mandhyata*. Along with vitiated *Vata*, alteration in *Guru* and *Sthira Guna* of *Kapha* causes *Srotorodha* with decrease in metabolism, increase in body weight and thickened skin. With the increase in *Guru* and *Picchila Guna* in body *Sira Shaithilya* takes place and thus the working mechanism of *Rasa Rakta Vikshepana* gets slow down and it affects *Rasa, Rakta, Sira* and *Lasika*. The blood gets too thick with low osmotic pressure as compared to the cells. Thus it will move from higher concentration to lower concentration. Hence, there occurs the accumulation of fluid giving rise to '*Shila Vat Shopham*'.

Arati: *Arati* is synonym of *Vedana*. Pain does not manifest without the involvement of *Vata*. Due to *Srotorodha*, *Gati* of *Vata* gets obstructed with alteration in *Chala, Sukshma, Ruksha Guna* of *Vata*. It causes increase in dryness of skin, discoloration and thickened skin.^[22,23] Pain in association with *Pitta* and *Kapha Dosha*, respectively the *Dahayukta Vedana* and *Manda Vedana* can be inferred due to alteration in *Guna* of the concerned *Dosha*.

Jwara: Intake of Excessive *Shleshmala Ahara Vihara* causes *Ama* formation with an increase in *Drava, Snigdha, Picchila* and *Kleda Guna* of *Kapha Dosha*. *Apya Mahabhuta* is predominant in *Kapha Dosha*; with an increase in *Kapha Dosha* subsequently

there occurs alteration in *Medo Dhatu* in the body. Along with the obstruction of *Medovaha Srotas*, *Swedhavaha Srotas* also gets obstructed as *Sweda* is *Mala* of *Medo Dhatu*. It does not able to restore the body temperature and thus causing *Jwara*.^[24-25]

<i>Hetu</i>	<i>Sira Shaithilya</i>	<i>Ama Manifestaton</i>	<i>Srotorodha</i>
Dosha involved	<i>Tridosha</i>	<i>Tridosha</i>	<i>Vata</i>
Agni Dusti	<i>Mandagni</i>	<i>Mandagni, Rasadhatvagnimandhya Medodhatvagnimandhya</i>	<i>Vishamagni</i>
Guna involved	<i>Drava, Guru, Sthira, Picchila</i>	<i>Kleda, Drava, Snigdha Picchila</i>	<i>Sukshma, Ruksha, Chala</i>
Karma Affected	<i>Sarana</i>	<i>Pachana</i>	<i>Gati</i>
Sroto Dushti	<i>Sanga, Vimargagamana</i>	<i>Sanga Vimargamana</i>	<i>Sanga, Vimargagamana</i>
Lakshanas	<i>Shopha</i>	<i>Jwara</i>	<i>Arati, Rukshata</i>

Shleepada is a *Tridoshaja Vyadhi* which is predominant of *Kapha Dosha*.^[6] *Acharya* has classified *Shleepada* into three types as *Vataja*, *Pittaja*, *Kaphaja* (Table 2B). *Acharya Bhela* has enumerated *Shleepada* into seven types but no detail has been mentioned.^[29] *Visheshya Lakshanas* (Table 2C) manifests pertaining to specific *Doshic* involvement as shown in table below.

Types of <i>Shleepada</i>	<i>Vataja shleepada</i>	<i>Pittaja shleepada</i>	<i>Kaphaja shleepada</i>
<i>Charaka</i>	-	-	-
<i>Sushruta</i>	+	+	+
<i>Vagbhata</i>	+	+	+
<i>Madhava</i>	+	+	+
<i>Bhavaprakasha</i>	+	+	+
<i>Yogaratanakara</i>	+	+	+

<i>Dosha Lakshana</i>	<i>Vataja Shleepada</i>	<i>Pittaja Shleepada</i>	<i>Kaphaja Shleepada</i>
<i>Sushruta</i> ^[26]	<i>Khara, Krushna, Parusha, Animitta Anila Ruja</i>	<i>Peetav Avbasa, Ishat Mridu, Jwara, Daha</i>	<i>Shweta, Snigdha, Mandavedana, Bharikam Mahagranthikam Kantaka Rupachitam</i>
<i>Madhava</i> ^{[27], <i>Bhavaprakash</i>^{[28], <i>Yogaratanakara</i>^[30]}}	<i>Krushna, Ruksha, Sphutita, Teevra Vedana, Animitta Ruja, Jwara</i>	<i>Peeta Sankasham, Daha, Jwara, Mridu Shotha</i>	<i>Snigdha Varna, Shweta, Pandu, Guru, Sthira</i>
<i>Vagbhata</i> ^[2]	<i>Paripotayuta, Krishnam, Animitaja, Khara, Ruksha</i>	<i>Peeta Varna Twak, Daha, Jwara</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha, Mamsa Ankurabruhata</i>

Upashaya and Pathya (Relieving Factors)

Langana (Fasting therapy), *Alepanana* (External application), *Swedana* (Fomentation), *Rechana* (Purgation therapy), *Raktamokshana* (Blood Letting), *Kaphaghna Ushna Upchara*^[30] and *Siraveda* in *Vataja shleepada* 4 Angul above *Gulfa Sandhi* (Ankle Joint), *Pittaja* 4 Angul below *Gulfa Sandhi*, *Kaphaja* 4 Angul above *Shipra Marma* in foot relieves *Shleepada*. *Paneeya Kshara* (Alkaline preparation) is also indicated.^[31] Intake of *Shakhotak Valka Kwatha* (decoction of *Streblus asper*) along with *Gomutra* relieves *Shleepada*.^[32]

Wholesome Diet consists of *Yava Anna* (Barley), *Sarshapa Taila* (Mustard Oil), *Kurma Mamsa* (flesh of Tortoise).^[33] *Purana*, *Shashtika Shali* (varieties of Rice), *Yava*, *Kulatha* (*Macrotyloma uniflorum*), *Lashuna* (*Allium sativum*), *Patola* (*Trichosanthes dioica*), *Shobhanjan* (*Moringa oleifera*), *Karvellaka* (*Momordica charantia*), *Upodika* (*Basella rubra*), *Punarnava Mula* (*Boerhavia diffusa*), *Eranda Taila* (*Ricinus communis*), *Gomutra*, *Katu Tikta Rasa Pradhana Dravya*, *Deepaniya Padartha* are mentioned as *Pathya*.^[34]

Anupshaya and Apathya (Aggravating Factors)

Pishtanna, *Dugdha Vikruti*, *Guda*, *Anupa Jeeva Mamsa*, *Madhura Amla Rasa Pradhana Padartha*, *Paariyaatra*, *Vindya*, *Sindhu Jala*, *Picchila Padartha*, *Guru Padartha* and *Abhishyandi Padartha* are considered as unwholesome.^[35]

Samprapti (Pathogenesis) [6, 19, 27, 36]

(Flowchart 1, Samprapti of Shleepada)

Samprapti mentions about the progression of disease. It plays a significant role in deciding the treatment protocol and management of disease.

Pradhana Samprapti: Kapha Pradhana Tridoshaja

Vidhi Samprapti: Nija , Doshaja, Yapyya, Shastra Kriya Sadhya Vyadhi

Vikalpa Samprapti:Kapha (Drava Guna, Snigdha Guna, Sthira Guna), Vata (Ruksha Guna, Sukshma, Chala), Pitta (Ushna Guna, Drava Guna)

Samkhya Samprapti: Three Types, Seven types of Shleepada

Bala Samprapti: Roga Bala is more

Kala Samprapti: All age groups (not specified)

Samprapti Ghataka (Components of Pathogenesis)

Table 3 Samprapti Ghataka of Shleepada

Table 3 Samprapti Ghataka of Shleepada	
Dosha	Kapha Pradhana Tridosha [6]
Dushya	Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Medas [19,37],Lasika
Srotas	Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Mamsavaha, Medovaha
Adhithana	Twak [3],Vankshana,Uru, Jaanu, Jangha
Srotodushti	Sanga,Vimargagamana
Swabhava	Chirakari
Agni	Jatharagnijanya Mandhya, Dhatvagnijanya Mandhya
Ama	Jatharagnijanya Ama, Dhatvagnijanya Ama
Udbhava Sthana	Amashaya
Sanchara Sthana	Sarva Sharira
Vyakta Sthana	Adhobhaga Shopha [36], Karna, Netra, Shishna, Oshtha and Nasa Gata Shopha [6]
Rogamarga	Bahya [38]
Sadhyasadhyata	If Shleepada persists for more than one year and it grows bigger in size resembling to that of an ant hill and exudates fluid it is Asadhya [6] If Shleepada manifests with bigger size and exudates, associated with itching is considered as Asadhya [8]
Updrava	In Kapha Prakruti person, due to Kaphaja Ahaara Vihara if symptoms of Tridosha arises with Srava, Unnata and is associated with Kandu, then Vyadhi manifested is termed as Achikitsya [39]
Arishta Lakshana	Not mentioned

Dushita Jala Sevana, Kaphavardhaka Ahara Vihara aggravates the *Kapha Dosha* predominantly along with *Tridosha*. As *Kapha Dosha* is *Ashrayee to Rasa Dhatu*, it influences the *Prakruta Karma* of *Rasa Dhatu*. Due to *Sneha Samana Guna* of *Kapha*, *Pitta* also gets vitiated. *Pitta Dosha* is *Ashrayee to Rakta Dhatu* and thus does the *Dusti* of *Rakta*. *Kapha* is *Ashrayee to Mamsa* and does the vitiation of *Mamsa Dhatu* and *Medo Dhatu*. The *Rasavaha Srotas*, *Raktavaha Srotas*, *Mamsavaha Srotas* and *Medovaha Srotas* are thus involved and have its significance. Due to *Sanga*, the *Prakruta Gati* of *Dosha* is deranged followed by *Vimarga Gamana*. There occurs the *Adhobhaga Gamana* of *Prakupita Dosha*. It will affect the *Twak (Rohini Layer)* which is regarded as the seat of *Shleepada*^[3]. They take their *Ashraya* in *Pada* and gradually results in manifestation of *Shopha*. Due to *Kapha Dosha* involvement *Shleepada* is said to be *Amashaya Samutha Vyadhi*. In due course of time, *Shopha* will turn into hard like consistency and thus manifests as *Shleepada* (Flowchart1). As per *Dosha* involvement *Shleepada* manifests as *Vataja*, *Pittaja* and *Kaphaja*. *Shleepada* is said to be of bad prognosis if persists for more than one year and grows in size associated with severe itching [6,8] (Table 3)

CONCLUSION

Shleepada is *Kapha Pradhana Tridoshaja Vyadhi* which is caused by *Dusta Jala Sevana and Mithya Ahara Vihara Sevana*. It manifests as '*Shila Vat Shopham*' which starts from groin and gradually extends to the feet. *Shleepada* does not manifest without the involvement of *Kapha*. Pathogenesis of *Shleepada* has been discussed in detail to develop an insight to arrest the progression of the disease and to plan the *Chikitsa* (Treatment) accordingly in order to promote the health and wellbeing of the population.

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